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My Phd Research and Study on International Economics by Iqbal Shaukat

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Abstract

Economics Development is the important part of nation life. Every nation want the economic development. Economic Development only possible when we study the international economics. International economics built the vision of the nation. With the concept of International nation got the destination of development. International economics provide the path how the nations got the economic development. International economics models are very viable for every nation. If the nation adopted the models of other countries, they can achieve the goal of economics growth and development.

Keywords: international, economics. development.

Introduction

International economics is very beneficial for the students and scholar and economist. International economics provide the guideline how to get the goal of economics growth and development. In the international economics we read the economics growth and development model of various countries. We can learn the lesson how the goal of economics growth and development can be achieved in the era of globalization. International economics provide the path of economic stability and development.

Literature Review

International economics help the countries built the good relationship. In the presence of international economics all the countries avoid conflict. In the case of conflict between the countries, they built good relationship. International economics provide the path how the both countries can improve the relations. International economics provide the guideline how to formulate the good trade policies which is very suitable for the nations. International economics is very important for such nations which are not developed. With the help of international economics rich countries help the poor countries and countries whose are below the poverty line, as far as the economic model of the developed countries provide the policies making guide line to the under developed countries. In international economics we follow the welfare policies of other of developed countries. In the age of modernization of international economics developed countries provide the guide line how the resources is utilized. International economics provide the how the good relationship among countries. In the case of disaster, because of international economics provide the financial and logistics support to such countries which are facing the natural climates. In various countries lot of natural resources, international economics provide the guidance how the resources are utilized. In various countries the education system not according to international standers, international economics provide the opportunity to improve the education system. Because of international economics the students of the many countries got the degree education in various countries. International economics provide the opportunity how to enhance the corporation in the medical fields. Countries provide the help each other to built good medical system. International economics

provide the base how the countries can help the patients. In the present of international economics countries can increase the relationship for the industrial growth and development. Developed countries can provide the technical assistance to under developed countries for the growth of industries. In the international economics both countries can enhance the relationship in the field of agriculture sector, for example if one country have the need of some agriculture crops, other country can provide the crops. In the presence of international economics developed countries can provide the equipment for example tractors. International economics provide the road map how to give the vocational training to other countries. In the international economics we create the good relationship with institutes. International financial institutions provide the support in bad economics circumstances. International economics provide the guide how the countries can encourage the investment. International economics provide the guide line how the investment is encourage and increase in various countries. International economics provide the guide line how to decrease the duty regime for various countries. International economics can provide the guide line how to control the inflation in the country. International economics provide the guide line how to adopted the price mechanism of the commodities. In the international economics we study the environment of other countries. In the present of international economics we can study the marketing environment of other countries. International economics provide the guide line regarding the financial and economics laws of other countries. International economics provide the line how to increase the economics relationship with other countries. In the International economics we study the monetary and fiscal policies of other countries. International economics provide the analysis regarding the per capita and national income. In the international economics we study how the gross domestic product increase by countries. When we study the international economics we know how to countries face the economics challenges. [1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9],[10],[11],[13].

Literature Review Subjective Study of International Economics

In the international economics we study about the balance of trade of various countries with the rest of world. In the international economics we study about the monetary and fiscal policies of various countries. We can get the benefit from the fiscal and monetary policy guidelines. In the international economics study regarding the balance of trade countries with the rest of world. In the international economics we study about the balance of payment. International economics provide the guide how developed countries improve the balance of payment with the rest of world. Global Taxation system are discussed in the international economics. Different management theory and practice are studied in the international economics. Different currency system are studied and discussed in the international economics. In the international economics we study about the banking currency and finance system of the various countries. In the international economics we study about the different trade agreements which were settled between the various countries in the past years. The economics growth are discussed in the international economics. Economic Development are discussed in the international economics. In the international economics we study the about rate of economic development. In the international economics we study about the different countries facilities index regarding the basic facility of lives. Global economic history are discussed in the international economics. In the international economics we study about the role of international financial institutes in the economics Development. Various operation management models are discussed in the international management, we discussed how the operation management play that dynamic role in the economics growth of the countries. Various marketing strategies are discussed in the international economics. In the international economics we study about the labour laws of various countries. In the international economics we study about corporate laws and companies laws of developed and developing countries. International economics provide the study how the countries came over economics recession and crises. In the international economics we study the data about the economic growth of various countries.

[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9],[10],[13].

Best Few Models of International Economics.

Japan Is the Famous Model in International Economics

Because the good operation management, they achieved the highest growth of Development, Japan adopted the good supply chain management, because of this good supply chain management they came over all economics difficulties. In Japan the production management is very good because of good production management they utilized all the resources very good. Japan achieved the optimum level of utilization of resources. Japan adopted such models of material which is very use full for the production. In the recent years Japan achieved very repaid growth in the automobile industry. They achieved the highest record in the production in the automobile production. South Korea adopted the good operation management system. They adopted such method which increase the GDP.

Korea Is Best Model in the International Economics

In In Korea the automobile sector is very developed and achieved the growth because of utilization of resources. In the recent years South Korea achieved the highest growth of economic growth and development. South Korea operation management model is the great symbol of other countries which are moving on the way of growth and development.

China is the big example of economic growth and development. They achieved the highest economic growth with the help of good operation management system. In china the utilization of resources very optimum level. Because of the good operation management they achieved the target of cost effectiveness. In this era of globalization china is the main hub of investment because of viable operation management. [1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9],[12].

Research Regarding the International Economics Study

I Conducted the Qualitative and Quantitative Research

My hypothesis that global economics study very important for the student, scholar, and economics is very important regarding the economics growth and development.

Table.

Category.	yes.	No
Accountant	3.	0
MBA.	4	0
M.Com.	5.	0

Table 2:

Cetogory	Yes.	No
Economist.	4.	0
Tax consultant	5.	0
Accountant.	6.	0

Majority of the audience agreed that the global economics subjects are very important for the scholar, student and economist for the country economics growth and development.

Conclusion

It is to be concluded that the global economics is very beneficial for the students and scholar and economist. international economics provide the guideline how to get the goal of economics growth and development. in the international economics we read the economics growth and development model of various countries. we can learn the lesson how the goal of economics growth and development can be achieved in the era of globalization. international economics provide the path of economic stability and development.

References

1. Barrett, R. (2003). Vocational business: Training, developing and motivating people. Business & Economics.
2. Drucker, P. F. (1999, March–April). Managing oneself. Harvard Business Review.
3. Drucker, P. F. (2006). The effective executive: The definitive guide to getting the right things done. McGraw-Hill.
4. DuBrin, A. J. (2009). Essentials of management (8th ed.). Mason, OH: Thomson Business & Economics. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e317052004-001>
5. James Rauch (2008). "Growth and international trade," The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics. 2nd Edition. Abstract.
6. Smith, Charles (2007). International Trade and Globalisation, 3rd edition. Stocksfield: Anforme. ISBN 978-1-905504-10-7.
7. Henry Thompson (2011). "International Economics: Global Markets and Competition (3rd Edition)" Abstract.
8. Fayol, H. (2015). Henri Fayol, the manager. Jean-Louis Peaucelle (Ed.). Routledge.
9. Gulshan, S. S., & Prasad, L. (n.d.). Management principles and practices. Excel Books India.
10. Hanna, M., & Newman, W. R. (2007). Integrated operations management: A supply chain perspective (2nd ed.). Thomson/South-Western.
11. Heizer, J., Render, B., & Munson, C. (2020). Operations management: Sustainability and supply chain management (13th ed.). Pearson.
12. Heizer, J., & Render, B. (2011). Operations management (10th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson.
13. Koontz, H. (n.d.). Essentials of management (McGraw-Hill series in management). McGraw-Hill.
14. Koontz, H. (n.d.). Principles of management: An analysis of managerial functions. McGraw-Hill.
15. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2006). Marketing management (12th ed.). Pearson.
16. Mankiw, N. G. (2021). Principles of economics (9th ed.). Cengage Learning.